

The Paris Region Fellowship Programme

Calls

Short guide

2020 & 2021

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The Paris Region Fellowship Programme

This short guide was conceived to provide key information on the Paris Region Fellowship Programme to all interested parties. Researchers can refer to this document to prepare their application to the programme and find useful contact information.

SUMMARY

**Overview of the Paris Region
Fellowship Programme**

Page 3

Domains of Major Interest (DMI)

Page 4

**Benefits and features of the Paris
Region Fellowship Programme**

Page 5

Application process

Page 6

Recruitment process

Page 7

Timing of the calls

Page 8

Evaluation & selection criteria

Page 9

The Paris Region Fellowship Programme

ParisRegionFP will reinforce network structuration and complete the existing programmes of the Paris Region and its partners for increased impact, by focusing on the recruitment and training of international emerging leaders to foster research and innovation in the Paris Region, in France.

OVERVIEW

The Paris Region ranks among the most competitive regions in the world for higher education, research and development, innovation and entrepreneurship.

The Paris Region Fellowship Programme (ParisRegionFP) aims to foster excellence in research, by training and developing international mobility and careers of outstanding researchers at post-doctoral level from a large panel of disciplines and of all nationalities.

These Experienced Researchers (ER) will design and implement their original research project in a first-class research group of their choice belonging preferably to one of the 13 "Domain of Major Interest" (DMI) labels endorsed by the Paris Region. The DMIs are key research sectors on which the Paris Region focuses policy support and investments to strengthen its international attractiveness and intersectoral mobility.

Two calls of 2-year postdoctoral fellowships, 26 applications each, are planned to recruit a total of 52 ERs.

ParisRegionFP will offer a novel international, interdisciplinary and intersectoral training programme for ERs, covering scientific, academic and industrial topics in the identified key sectors (or DMI scientific themes) as well as hands-on knowledge in non-research oriented transferable skills. The educational and research programme will be implemented by leading universities and 20 extra-academic partner organisations, covering actors from prestigious culture-related organisations and human resource actors to large industries and SMEs in various economic sectors.

The scientific actors will ensure infrastructure capacity and high-level environment to conduct excellent research. Extra-academic partners will contribute to the implementation of ParisRegionFP by hosting ERs during secondments or visits and/or by providing training, mentoring or career development opportunities.

Domains of Major Interest

23 labs
European leadership of Paris region in astrophysics
www.dimacav-plus.fr

94 labs
Exceptional heritage infrastructures and ancient materials
www.dim-map.fr

37 labs
High concentration of internationally-renowned centers in mathematics
www.dim-mathinnov.fr

20 labs
OneHealth, one world: international network on environmental health, human health and animal health
www.dim1health.com

47 labs
Internationally-renowned and interdisciplinary research groups in porous solids science
www.respore.fr

32 labs
Strongest European hotspot of academic teams in quantum physics and technologies
www.sirteq.org

36 labs
Concentration of high-level research labs and European projects in air quality and health
www.dim-qi2.fr

27 labs
Paris region as a pioneer in gene therapy with strong intersectoral partnerships
www.dim-tg.org

25 labs
Expert groups on microfluidics, biophotonics and imaging for life science
www.dim-elicit.fr

30 labs
International reputation of the consortium in computer science
www.dim-rfsi.fr

23 labs
High concentration of prestigious infrastructures and research groups in digital humanities
www.dim-humanites-numeriques.fr

12 labs
Arabic and Islamic history, society, culture
phasif.fr

42 labs
Exceptional infrastructures and databases for research in ageing
www.gerondif.org

ParisRegionFP

Benefits

Main features of the programme

WHY TO APPLY ?

RECRUITMENT CONDITIONS

- Benefit from a 2-year post-doctoral research fellowship with a minimum gross salary of 4740€/ month, and supplementary budget for research and travel expenses

TRAINING PROGRAMME

- Develop technical and transferable (non-research related) skills thanks to training carried out by professional partners

INDIVIDUAL-DRIVEN MOBILITY

- Develop your research topic and choose your host group among the renowned Paris area research organisations

CAREER DEVELOPMENT

- Get mentoring & career development support
- Benefit from secondment opportunities both in academic and non-academic sectors

PRESTIGIOUS ENVIRONMENT

- Be part of world-class research environment, with exceptional infrastructure capacities
- Increase networking possibilities

QUALITY OF LIFE

- Live in Paris region thanks to facilitated logistic and welcoming services
- Get support provided for accompanying family members

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Application process

Main requirements of the programme

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

- Compliance with the Marie Skłodowska-Curie **mobility rule**: applicants must not have resided or carried out their main activity (work, studies, etc.) in France for more than 12 months in the last three years before the call deadline;
- At the time of recruitment, applicants must be in possession of a **doctoral degree** (or have at least four years of full-time equivalent research experience);
- Applicants can **choose a host research group** belonging to one of the “Domains of Major Interest” (around 450 laboratories) to **develop the research project** of their choice. The programme accepts also host laboratories in the Paris Region not part of the DMIs.
- No other restrictions are implemented, the Paris Region applies strict **equal opportunity principles** for candidates’ selection and recruitment.
- Any **ethical issues** linked to the research project must be clarified by the Ethics self-assessment.

APPLICATION

Applicants need to apply to the fellowship through the call platform following the key dates indicated on <https://parisregionfp.sciencescall.org/> (1st call October 2020, 2nd call October, 21st, 2021). Incomplete applications will not be eligible, and no applications will be accepted after the call closure. The application contains the following documents:

- **Curriculum Vitae** and **track record**.
- **Research project** description. Based on **individual-driven mobility principle**, fellows will freely choose a research topic and the appropriate host (and secondment) organization(s) and supervisor(s) fitting their individual needs.
- **PhD degree** transcript and/or appropriate **work certificate(s)**.
- Proof of identity.
- **Declaration** of honor on the **mobility rule**.
- 2 **recommendation** letters.
- **Ethics self-assessment** form.

FURTHER INFORMATION

- parisregion.eu
- prfp@iledefrance.fr

APPLY VIA

parisregionfp.sciencescall.org

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Recruitment process

Main features of the process

Eligibility and ethical issues check

The applicants will be informed of their eligibility (completeness, compliance, ethical issues) by e-mail after the call closure. Only eligible applicants will be evaluated at the 1st selection round.

Evaluation by international / independent experts

Each application will be evaluated by 2 international / independent experts. They will evaluate both the profile of the candidate and the research project. If an application gets divergent evaluations from two international / independent experts, this application will be submitted to a third international / independent expert for assessment according to the evaluation criteria defined hereafter. An independent Selection Committee will rank the applications. Shortlisted candidates will be invited for the 2nd selection round (interviews).

Interview of shortlisted candidates

The online interview will consist of a 10-minute presentation followed by a 10-minute discussion between the candidate and the Interview Evaluation Panel members composed by the Selection Committee.

Funding decision

The Regional Scientific Council will formally approve the final list of selected candidates.

Feedback & redress procedure

All candidates will be informed of the results and next steps by e-mail. Redress/appeal possibility is available at all stages of the procedure by contacting: prfp@iledefrance.fr.

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Timing of the calls

Indicative timing for the 1st call

Indicative timing for the 2nd call

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Evaluation & selection criteria

1st round: evaluation / review of applications

APPLICATION QUALIFICATIONS

30%

- Quality of the CV
- Excellence of the track record

RESEARCH PROJECT (EXCELLENCE)

50%

- Quality, innovative aspects and feasibility of the research project
- Interdisciplinary and international aspects of the project
- Exposure to intersectoral (extra-academic) sector

CAREER DEVELOPMENT

20%

- Impact of the project on the professional career development

2nd round: interviews

PROFILE OF THE CANDIDATE

30%

- Work experience both in the academic and private sectors
- International experience
- Cross-domain experience

RESEARCH PROJECT (IMPACT & IMPLEMENTATION)

40%

- Quality and novelty of the research project
- Alignment with the DMI's/ laboratory's thematic perimeter
- Coherence and effectiveness of the work plan

POTENTIAL OF THE CANDIDATE

30%

- Potential for leadership
- Openness and creativity
- Career path vision

TRESHOLD and SCORING: Each criteria is scored from 1 to 5, from poor to excellent. The applicants should reach a threshold score of 7/10 to be interviewed.